

Coalescing and break-up of viscous drops with surface tension through the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

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ABSTRACT

A study on the phenomena of drop coalescence and break-up is tackled for viscous flows with surface tension. The proposed analysis focuses on single-phase problems and is carried on by using the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH). This scheme allows for a straightforward treatment of the free surface and for an accurate description of the energy balance during the most delicate stages of coalescence and break-up. This latter aspect, combined with theoretical relations on the surface-tension energy, allowed for an in-depth characterization of the above phenomena in terms of energy evolution. A number of numerical test cases are considered in order to support and illustrate the main findings of the proposed work.

1. Introduction

Surface tension has always been a fascinating phenomenon and an intriguing topic for scientists. The variety of physical processes and problems in which it plays an important role is huge, and ranges from drop formation and break-up in multi-phase flows, to wetting effects, film flows and microfluidics.

The influence of surface tension on the flow dynamics represents a challenging problem, both in terms of physical description and theoretical modeling, as well as in its numerical implementation. In particular, the evolution of viscous drops of Newtonian fluids belongs to the above context and their break-up and collision represents an extreme case of the drop interaction. First studies on this problem dates back to 150 years ago [1]. Through the years a large number of works has been devoted to this topic by theoretical [2–5], experimental, [6–9] and numerical approaches [10–14]. The aim of the present work is to give a further contribution to this subject by numerically studying the phenomena of drop coalescence and break-up with specific focus on the energy budget. Starting from the seminal work by [3], we study the energy singularities arising when portions of the free surface remain entrapped during drop coalescence or, equivalently, ligaments are severed during drop breakup. This is done through the use of a meshless particle method, namely the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH). This choice is motivated by two main features that characterize such a scheme and that make it particularly suitable for the modeling of free-surface problems.

First, the SPH does not need an explicit enforcement of the kinematic and dynamic boundary conditions along the free surface. As shown in [15], the latter condition is implicitly satisfied in an integral mean along the interface, while the former one is satisfied as a consequence of the Lagrangian nature of the scheme along the free-surface.

Secondly, the SPH scheme allows for a straightforward inspection of the energy contributions coming from the different physical terms inside the Navier–Stokes equations. In the last decade, the analysis of the energy balance has become a powerful tool in the SPH literature [16–19] and, in the present framework, is used in combination with appropriate theoretical relations for surface

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tension in order to accurately characterize the most delicate stages of the drop coalescence and break-up. In particular, a compound approach is derived for the estimation of the energy associated with the surface tension, basing on two different techniques. The first one rests on theoretical results that relate the surface tension energy to the free-surface length. The second technique is based on the computation of the work done by the surface tension through the SPH model. Both techniques are used to follow the evolution of the surface tension energy, allowing for an in-depth characterization of the initial stages of coalescence and of the free-surface separation during the break-up. A validation and a critical discussion on the limits of these approaches have been provided in [19].

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the governing equations and the physical framework, Section 3 describes the adopted SPH model and its energy balance, while Section 4 illustrates the numerical results. Finally, Section 5 rounds the paper providing a discussion of the main findings. As a further important contribution, we highlight the presence of a number of appendices devoted to the demonstration of the theoretical results that are used in the paper. These sections can be regarded as a simple reference for the description of the interface dynamics, since they provide proofs of well-known relations without relying on advanced concepts of differential geometry.

2. Governing equations

In the present work we consider single-phase problems consisting in the evolution of an incompressible Newtonian fluid in a generic domain Ω without solid boundaries and external forces. Phase changes and miscibility phenomena are not considered. The flow evolution is governed by the Navier–Stokes Equations (NSEs) that in Lagrangian formalism read as below:

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \\ \rho_0 \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} \\ \frac{D\mathbf{x}}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

in which D/Dt is the Lagrangian derivative, \mathbf{u} is the flow velocity, \mathbf{x} the position of the material points, ρ_0 is the fluid density (constant) and \mathbf{T} is the stress tensor. For a Newtonian fluid the latter is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{T} = -p\mathbf{I} + 2\mu\mathbf{D} \quad (2)$$

where p is the pressure field, \mathbf{D} is the strain-rate tensor and μ is the dynamic viscosity. Since we consider the evolution of a single fluid without solid boundaries, only surface tension acts along the boundary of the domain (indicated hereinafter by $\partial\Omega_F$). This implies that the stress along the free surface is:

$$\mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \sigma \kappa \mathbf{n} \quad \forall \mathbf{r} \in \partial\Omega_F \quad (3)$$

where the right-hand side is the Young–Laplace equation. Here, σ is the surface tension coefficient, \mathbf{n} is the normal unit vector of $\partial\Omega_F$ pointing outward Ω and $\kappa = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is the curvature of the surface (here defined as twice the mean curvature). The Young–Laplace equation in (3) satisfies the conservation of linear and angular momenta. This means that if $\partial\Omega_F$ is a *closed* free surface, the following relations hold true:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega_F} \kappa \mathbf{n} dS = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\partial\Omega_F} \mathbf{x} \times (\kappa \mathbf{n}) dS = 0. \quad (4)$$

The former equalities are proved, for example, in [20,21]. Simpler proofs are, however, provided in the [Appendix A](#).

The energy equation for the NSEs with surface tension is obtained by multiplying the momentum equation for \mathbf{u} and integrating over the volume Ω . Then, using the divergence theorem and the condition (3) along the free surface, we find:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_{\Omega} \rho_0 \frac{\|\mathbf{u}\|^2}{2} dV = \sigma \int_{\partial\Omega_F} \kappa (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) dS - 2\mu \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{D} : \mathbf{D} dV \quad (5)$$

As shown in [Appendix B](#), the integral related to the surface tensions is equivalent to the material derivative of the surface area, namely:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega_F} \kappa (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) dS = -\frac{D}{Dt} \left(\int_{\partial\Omega_F} dS \right) \quad (6)$$

This allows one to rearrange the energy equation in the following compact form:

$$\frac{D\mathcal{E}_K}{Dt} + \frac{D\mathcal{E}_\sigma}{Dt} = \mathcal{P}_v \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{E}_K is the kinetic energy, $\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma \mathcal{L}_F$ is the surface tension energy (here \mathcal{L}_F is the free-surface area) and, finally, \mathcal{P}_v indicates dissipated by viscous effects.

Since we do not consider external forcing terms, the flows studied in the present work only depends on the Reynolds and Weber numbers defined as:

$$\text{Re} = \frac{\rho_0 U_{ref} L}{\mu}, \quad \text{We} = \frac{\rho_0 U_{ref}^2 L}{\sigma}$$

where U_{ref} and L are the reference velocity and length of the problem at hand respectively.

2.1. Modeling the surface tension

In this section we provide a brief summary of the different approaches used to include the surface tension in the Navier–Stokes equations along with the related theoretical framework. Specifically, we assume that the boundary $\partial\Omega_F$ is a regular manifold so that it can be represented as the zero-level of an implicit function, that is $F(x, t) = 0$. The unit vector normal to $\partial\Omega_F$ is defined as $\mathbf{n} = \nabla F / \|\nabla F\|$ and is assumed to point outward. This means that $F(x, t) > 0$ outside the domain Ω and $F(x, t) < 0$ inside Ω . Through the above approach the definition of the vector \mathbf{n} is not restricted to the points belonging to the free surface but is automatically extended out of it.

The first model dates back to [22] where the surface tension is represented as a continuous force across an interface, rather than as a boundary value condition on the interface. This is done, in fact, by using a diffuse domain approach through the definition of a proper color function which depends on F and on a dimensionless parameter ϵ , namely $C_\epsilon(F)$. The color function can be defined in several different ways. Here, we require it to be a smooth, positive, monotonic increasing function of F and to satisfy the following properties:

$$C_\epsilon(0) = 1/2 \quad \forall \epsilon \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} C_\epsilon(F) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } F > 0 \\ 1/2 & \text{if } F = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } F < 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Note that the latter conditions are reversed for a monotonic decreasing function. The properties described in (8) imply $\mathbf{n} = \nabla F / \|\nabla F\| = \nabla C_\epsilon / \|\nabla C_\epsilon\| \quad \forall \epsilon$. Using the color function, [22] defined the so-called Continuum Surface Force (CSF) method, in which the surface tension is represented by the following volume force concentrated in the neighborhood of the interface $\partial\Omega_F$:

$$\mathbf{F}^\sigma = \sigma \kappa \mathbf{n} \delta_\epsilon, \quad (9)$$

where $\delta_\epsilon = 2 \|\nabla C_\epsilon\|$. In Appendix C we prove that δ_ϵ tends to a Dirac distribution along $\partial\Omega$ for ϵ going to zero. As shown in [10] (and in a shorter manner in the Appendix C), it is possible to rearrange the expression (9) in the form of a tensor gradient, that is:

$$\mathbf{F}^\sigma = \nabla \cdot \mathbb{T}^S \quad \text{where} \quad \mathbb{T}^S = \sigma \|\nabla C_\epsilon\| (\mathbb{I} - \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n}). \quad (10)$$

Both formulations are equivalent at the continuum but differ when they are represented at the discrete. The formulation in (10) is suitable for numerical models that allow for the conservation of linear and angular momenta. In the SPH framework, however, it is generally less stable than the one described in (9). About this topic, the interested reader is addressed to the discussion of [23].

3. Numerical model

The numerical results presented in this work are obtained by using the Regularized High-Order Diffusive Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics scheme (RHOD-SPH) derived in Michel et al. [24]. This choice is motivated by the fact that such a scheme proved particularly suited for the modeling of free surface flows characterized by large and complex deformations.

The RHOD-SPH belongs to the class of weakly-compressible Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics schemes (WC-SPH hereinafter) which are commonly used in SPH to approximate the evolution of incompressible fluids. In this framework, the flow evolution is governed by the Navier–Stokes Equations for compressible barotropic fluids. In Lagrangian formalism they read:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}, \\ \rho \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot \mathbb{T}, \\ \frac{Dx}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}, \quad p = F(\rho), \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where F is the state equation for barotropic fluids. In WC-SPH the liquid phase is modeled as a weakly-compressible Newtonian fluid, i.e. density variations are always smaller than 1% with respect to the reference density ρ_0 . Under this condition, a linearized equation of state is used, that is:

$$p = c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0), \quad (12)$$

and the speed of sound c_0 is modified for computational convenience. In order to ensure the weakly-compressible regime, however, the numerical speed of sound has to satisfy the following constraints:

$$c_0 \geq 10 \max \left(\Delta U_{max}, \sqrt{\frac{\Delta P_{max}}{\rho_0}}, \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\rho_0} |\kappa|_{max}} \right), \quad (13)$$

where $|\kappa|_{max}$, ΔU_{max} , ΔP_{max} are the maximum expected interface curvature (in absolute value), velocity variation and pressure variation during the time evolution.

In the framework of SPH, the fluid domain is discretized as a set of fluid particles moving with their own velocity and carrying the values of the fluid quantities (e.g., density, pressure etc.). No topological connections are defined among particles and the

differential operators are computed through convolution summations using a radial function with compact support. This is usually called weight or kernel function and is denoted through W . In the present work the C^2 -Wendland kernel is adopted [25]. At the discrete level, the governing equations of the RHOD-SPH are represented within a Quasi-Lagrangian framework as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\rho_i}{dt} &= -\rho_i \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}_i + \delta \mathbf{u}_i) + \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i) + \Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho \\ \rho_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} &= \mathbf{F}_i^p + \mathbf{F}_i^\mu + \mathbf{F}_i^{ad} + \mathbf{F}_i^\sigma + \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i) + \Theta_{i,Rie}^\mu \\ \frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} &= \mathbf{u}_i + \delta \mathbf{u}_i, \quad V_i(t) = m_i / \rho_i(t), \quad p_i = c_0^2 (\rho_i - \rho_0), \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where the subscript i refers to the generic i th particle while \mathbf{F}_i^p , \mathbf{F}_i^μ , \mathbf{F}_i^{ad} and \mathbf{F}_i^σ are respectively the pressure, the viscous, the acoustic damper defined in [18] and the surface tension forces acting on the particles. Symbols V_i and m_i denote the i th particle volume and mass respectively. The time derivative d/dt used in (14) indicates a quasi-Lagrangian derivative *i.e.*:

$$\frac{d(\bullet)}{dt} = \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial t} + \nabla(\bullet) \cdot (\mathbf{u} + \delta \mathbf{u}),$$

since the particles are moving with the modified velocity $(\mathbf{u} + \delta \mathbf{u})$. The vector $\delta \mathbf{u}$ is the Particle Shifting velocity used to regularize the particle spatial distribution during the motion. The specific law adopted in this work is the same reported in [24].

Accordingly, the continuity and the momentum equations contain terms with spatial derivatives of $\delta \mathbf{u}$ that are discretized as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}_i + \delta \mathbf{u}_i) &= \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i + \delta \mathbf{u}_j - \delta \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i) &= \sum_j (\rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i) &= \sum_j (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where the subscript j indicates the neighboring particles to the i th particle, while $W_{ij} = W(\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|)$. The symbols $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho$ and $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\mu$ in Eq. (14) denote the numerical diffusive terms that stem from the use of Riemann solvers. These are expressed following the approach described in Parshikov et al. [26]. For the sake of brevity they are not described in this work and the interested reader can find the details in [24].

Within the RHOD-SPH scheme the pressure forces \mathbf{F}_i^p are modeled as:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^p = \begin{cases} -\rho_i \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (p_j - p_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & \text{if } i \in \mathcal{I} \\ -\rho_i \sum_j (p_j + p_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where the subset \mathcal{I} refer to the inner fluid particles whose kernel support does not intersect the free surface (for more details see [24]). Here, \mathbb{L}_i is the renormalization matrix (see [27]), that is:

$$\mathbb{L}_i = \left[\sum_j (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) \otimes \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \right]^{-1} \quad (17)$$

The use of the renormalization matrix ensures the recovering of the exact gradient of a linear pressure field. The expression in Eq. (16) is, in fact, a switch from a non-conservative formulation on the inner particles to a conservative formulation for the particles belonging to the thin region close to the free-surface. Even though the exact conservation of momenta is lost, the proposed formulation is invariant by change of pressure reference (for internal flows), free from the Tensile Instability, and accurate in the evaluation of the pressure forces.

The viscous forces are represented through the classical Monaghan & Gingold model [28]:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^\mu = 2\mu(n+2) \sum_j \pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \quad \pi_{ij} = \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i)}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|^2}, \quad (18)$$

while the acoustic damper term is:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{ad} = \alpha_2 \rho_0 c_0 h \sum_j (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_j + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \quad (19)$$

where α_2 is a dimensionless parameter. Note that higher-order viscous operators are available in the literature as, for example, in [29,30]. Nonetheless, in the present work a classical Monaghan & Gingold operator is adopted as it is consistent for free-surface flows, whereas the formulations proposed by, *e.g.*, [31,32] exhibit certain inconsistencies. For instance, they predict nonzero viscous dissipation for a droplet undergoing pure rigid rotation. Since our analysis primarily focuses on the energy balance in droplet dynamics, we prefer the formulation of Monaghan & Gingold to avoid such inconsistencies. Additionally, we note that the latter viscous model has been extensively validated in the context of free-surface flows (see, *e.g.*, [33–35]).

The particle masses remain constant in time and they are set by using the initial particle volumes, V_{i0} , and the initial particle densities ρ_{i0} , i.e. $m_i = \rho_{i0} V_{i0}$. The particles are initially set on a lattice with an almost homogeneous spacing Δx . Hence the initial particles' volumes V_{i0} are evaluated as Δx^n where n is the number of spatial dimensions (see [36]).

3.1. The surface-tension model

In this section we specify the surface tension force model for \mathbf{F}_i^σ . In particular the Continuum Surface Force (CSF) model described in [37] has been implemented in the RHOD-SPH scheme. It belongs to the class of non-conservative models described in Eq. (9) and reads:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{F}_i^\sigma &= \sigma \kappa_i \mathbf{n}_i \delta_{Fi}, & \delta_{Fi} = 2 \left\| \sum_j \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \right\| \\ \kappa_i &= \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (\mathbf{n}_i - \mathbf{n}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, & \mathbf{n}_i = -\frac{\nabla \lambda_i}{\|\nabla \lambda_i\|}, \\ \nabla \lambda_i &= \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (\lambda_j - \lambda_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where λ_i is the minimum eigenvalue of \mathbb{L}_i^{-1} . More details can be found in [38]. As in [37], four critical corrections necessary for the description of thin jets or small drops are also implemented in order to increase accuracy and robustness of the scheme. The above scheme has been further validated in [19], proving to be robust and accurate.

3.2. Energy balance of the SPH model

The energy balance of the RHOD-SPH model is rather complex because of the presence of the power terms related to the shifting velocity, the regularized pressure gradient, the Riemann fluxes and the acoustic damper term. These terms, however, have been already studied in [18,24] and, consequently, are introduced in the present work without describing their complete expressions. The main focus is, in fact, on the action played by the surface tension force. In this context, the overall energy balance is used to check that the numerical dissipation introduced by the time integration scheme maintains negligible in comparison to the different energy terms. This guarantees that the simulations are not affected by any spurious additional dissipation.

The energy balance of the particle system is given below:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\mathcal{E}_K}{Dt} + \frac{D\mathcal{E}_C}{Dt} = \mathcal{P}_{diss} + \mathcal{P}_\sigma, \\ \mathcal{E}_K = \sum_i m_i \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_i\|^2}{2}, & \mathcal{E}_C = \sum_i m_i \int_{\rho_0}^{\rho_i} \frac{p(s)}{s^2} ds, \\ \mathcal{P}_{diss} = \mathcal{P}_v + \mathcal{P}_N, & \mathcal{P}_v = \sum_i (\mathbf{F}_i^\mu \cdot \mathbf{u}_i), & \mathcal{P}_\sigma = \sum_i (\mathbf{F}_i^\sigma \cdot \mathbf{u}_i), \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where \mathcal{E}_C is the (reversible) energy associated with the fluid compressibility, \mathcal{P}_σ is the power of the surface tension force and \mathcal{P}_v is the power dissipated by the viscous effects. Finally, \mathcal{P}_N is the power due to the action of the remaining numerical terms, that is:

$$\mathcal{P}_N = \mathcal{P}_{RR} + \mathcal{P}_{Rie} + \mathcal{P}_{ad}. \quad (22)$$

where \mathcal{P}_{RR} is the power term related to the particle shifting terms and the renormalized pressure gradient, \mathcal{P}_{Rie} is associated to the Riemann fluxes and \mathcal{P}_{ad} represents the power of the acoustic damper term. The expressions of the former two contributions are detailed in [24] while the last one is described in [18]. In principle, \mathcal{P}_N has not a definite sign, but it always works as a dissipation in the numerical scheme. For this reason, we denote by $\mathcal{P}_{diss} = \mathcal{P}_v + \mathcal{P}_N$ the overall power dissipated by the numerical scheme. Finally, we observe that \mathcal{P}_N , being related to numerical dissipation, is expected to converge to zero in the limit of $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$.

Before proceeding, we introduce the work done by the surface tension force:

$$\mathcal{W}_\sigma = \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_\sigma d\tau. \quad (23)$$

According to Eq. (6), \mathcal{P}_σ should be equal to $(-D\mathcal{E}_\sigma/Dt)$ and, consequently, \mathcal{W}_σ should be equal to $(\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} - \mathcal{E}_\sigma)$. Nonetheless, this is not true numerically, since the reversibility of \mathcal{W}_σ cannot be guaranteed in the adopted SPH model. In fact, the work \mathcal{W}_σ is intrinsically related to the CSF model (see Section 3.1) which is based on the evaluation of local quantities (like the normal and the curvature of the free-surface), without any direct connection with global quantities, like the surface energy associated to the deformation of $\partial\Omega_F$.

In order to check the numerical error of the SPH scheme in the evaluation of the surface energy, \mathcal{E}_σ is evaluated through a Level-Set function ϕ . The latter is obtained by using the algorithm described in [39] based on the interpolation of the particles set on a Cartesian mesh. Fig. 1 depicts an example of the level-set function for the six-mode oscillating drop (see [37] or Section 4.1 for details). When the contour level $\phi = 0$ is extracted, it is possible to evaluate the perimeter of the drop \mathcal{L}_F and, therefore, the surface energy $\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma \mathcal{L}_F$. It is worth noting that the level-set function is evaluated during a post-processing stage and for a limited number of time instants. Because of the CPU costs, it is not calculated at runtime for each time iteration.

Fig. 1. Left: Contour of the Level-set function ϕ calculated during the simulation of the six-mode oscillating drop described in Section 4.1. Right: enlarged view showing the Cartesian mesh adopted for the evaluation of ϕ and the normal vectors \mathbf{n}_i on $\partial\Omega_F$ calculated through Eq. (20). The red dash-dotted curve represents the $\phi = 0$ contour level.

Thanks to the above approach, at the end of each simulations it is possible to check to what extent the work \mathcal{W}_σ deviates from $(\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} - \mathcal{E}_\sigma)$ and if the deviation from the theoretical equality ultimately decreases when the spatial resolution $N = L/\Delta x$ increases. Note that the surface energy \mathcal{E}_σ is always evaluated geometrically through the Level-Set function ϕ , whereas the work of the surface tension forces \mathcal{W}_σ is evaluated from the CSF model described in Section 3.1 that is embedded in the SPH scheme.

About the energy associated with the fluid compressibility, namely \mathcal{E}_C , this appears as a consequence of the weak-compressibility assumption which is at the basis of the adopted SPH model. As a consequence of the constraint described in Eq. (13), it generally maintains small during the evolution.

3.3. Time integration scheme

A fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme is adopted for integrating in time Eq. (14) since this provides an optimal compromise among accuracy, stability and computational efficiency. On the other hand, the explicit nature of the time integrator imposes a stability criterion on the time step, Δt , which is computed as the minimum of the limitations imposed by physical information propagation times. These are:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta t_c = \Delta t_{ad} = 1.0 \left(\frac{h}{c_0} \right), & \Delta t_v = 0.125 \left(\frac{h^2}{\nu} \right), & \Delta t_\sigma = 0.1 \min_i \sqrt{\frac{\rho_0 h^2}{\sigma |\kappa_i|}}, \\ \Delta t_a = 0.25 \min_i \sqrt{\frac{h}{\|a_i\|}}, & \Delta t = \min(\Delta t_c, \Delta t_v, \Delta t_\sigma, \Delta t_a), \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

where $\|a_i\|$ is the particle acceleration. The last constraint is relevant in problems involving liquid impacts, whereas in the present work it is always negligible. The first constraint, namely Δt_c , is linked to the weak compressibility of the medium and to the related speed of sound c_0 . Setting $\alpha_2 = 1$, Δt_c coincides with the time step related to the use of the acoustic damper term, i.e. Δt_{ad} . The second and the third constraints, i.e. Δt_v and Δt_σ , are linked to viscous diffusion and to the surface tension model [31,40].

4. Results

The present section contains the results obtained from the applications of the numerical scheme to problems of drop coalescing and break-up. Before dealing with these dynamics, however, we consider a preliminary test on drops oscillating in zero gravity. The latter benchmark is used to check the consistency of the algorithm based on the comparison between \mathcal{W}_σ and \mathcal{E}_σ and, in general, the accuracy of the adopted numerical scheme. To this purpose it has been necessary to derive the exact solution of the linearized problem for the oscillating drop (see Appendix D), since the approximate solutions available in the literature were not accurate enough to describe the physical dynamics.

4.1. Oscillating drop in zero-gravity

In this section we consider the evolution of a viscous drop oscillating in zero-gravity subjected to surface tension. An approximate analytical solution for the linearized problem is obtained in [41] following the approach described in Lamb ([42], Section 329). The latter consists in the use of the energy equation for the estimation of the viscous damping. We highlight here that the above

procedure does not correspond to the exact solution of the linearized problem, since the free-surface condition is satisfied as an integral mean. Following the approach by Lamb, the fluid velocity is approximated through the following velocity potential in cylindrical coordinates:

$$\phi = \epsilon \frac{\phi_0}{n} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^n \cos(n\theta) \exp(-\alpha t) \tag{25}$$

which corresponds to the n th mode of oscillation. Here, R is the drop radius, ϕ_0 is the magnitude of the velocity potential, while α is the unknown coefficient to be found. Finally, $\epsilon = a/R$ is the parameter of the perturbation expansion, where a is the amplitude of the motion. Specifically, assuming $\epsilon \ll 1$, the following leading-order expression for α is obtained (see [41]):

$$\alpha^2 - 4\alpha n(n-1) \frac{\nu}{R^2} + n(n^2-1) \frac{\sigma}{\rho_0 R^3} = 0. \tag{26}$$

whose solution is:

$$\alpha = 2n(n-1) \frac{\nu}{R^2} \pm \sqrt{4n^2(n-1)^2 \frac{\nu^2}{R^4} - n(n^2-1) \frac{\sigma}{\rho_0 R^3}} \tag{27}$$

For the analysis that follows, it is convenient to introduce a further dimensionless number, namely:

$$\chi = \frac{\sigma R}{\rho_0 \nu^2}, \tag{28}$$

since this discerns between different regimes of motion. In particular, for $\chi > 4n(n-1)/(n+1)$, the argument under the square root of Eq. (27) is negative and the solution exhibits a damped oscillatory behavior. In this case the damping coefficient is:

$$\beta = \Re(\alpha) = 2n(n-1) \frac{\nu}{R^2} \tag{29}$$

whereas the angular frequency is:

$$\omega = \Im(\alpha) = \sqrt{n(n^2-1) \frac{\sigma}{\rho_0 R^3} - 4n^2(n-1)^2 \frac{\nu^2}{R^4}} \tag{30}$$

Conversely, for $\chi \leq 4n(n-1)/(n+1)$, both the roots of Eq. (26) are real (and positive) and, therefore, they represent a pure dissipation. Hereinafter we disregard the latter regime and consider only the damped oscillatory motion. Incidentally, we observe that the parameter χ is connected to another dimensionless number, namely the Ohnesorge number Oh , that relates the viscous forces to inertial and surface tension forces (see, for example, [43]). In particular, $\chi = Oh^2$.

In the numerical simulations we assume that the drop is initially circular. In this case, the velocity components for the damped-oscillatory regime are:

$$u_r = \epsilon \frac{\phi_0}{R} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{n-1} \cos(n\theta) \cos(\omega t + \psi) \exp(-\beta t) \tag{31}$$

$$u_\theta = -\epsilon \frac{\phi_0}{R} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{n-1} \sin(n\theta) \cos(\omega t + \psi) \exp(-\beta t). \tag{32}$$

where ψ is a phase shift. Setting $\phi_0 = \omega R^2$, we obtain the reference scale for the velocity field, namely $U_{ref} = \epsilon \phi_0/R = \epsilon \omega R$. Hence, the dimensionless numbers become:

$$\text{Re} = \epsilon \frac{\rho_0 \omega R^2}{\mu}, \quad \text{We} = \epsilon^2 \frac{\rho_0 \omega^2 R^3}{\sigma}, \quad \chi = \frac{\text{Re}^2}{\text{We}}, \tag{33}$$

where $L = R$ has been chosen as reference length. The solution for the free-surface evolution is:

$$r_{FS} = R + \frac{\epsilon \phi_0}{(\omega^2 + \beta^2) R} \cos(n\theta) [\omega \sin(\omega t + \psi) - \beta \cos(\omega t + \psi)] \exp(-\beta t). \tag{34}$$

Imposing the drop to be initially circular, we obtain $\psi = \arctan(\beta/\omega)$.

The expression for the pressure field is not provided in [41] and is derived by substituting the approximate solution for the velocity field in the Bernoulli equation. According to Eq. (3), the leading order of the pressure field along the free surface is imposed to be equal to the Laplace pressure, i.e. $P_{laplace} = \sigma/R$. Hence, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{p}{\rho_0} &= \frac{P_{laplace}}{\rho_0} + \epsilon \frac{\phi_0}{n} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^n \cos(n\theta) [\beta \cos(\omega t) + \omega \sin(\omega t)] \exp(-\beta t) \\ &+ \frac{\epsilon^2 \phi_0^2}{2 R^2} \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{2n-2} \right] \cos(\omega t + \psi)^2 \exp(-2\beta t). \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Incidentally, we observe that the pressure field along the circumference at the initial time is not identically equal to $P_{laplace}$. This is caused by the presence of a non-null viscous stress along the free surface (see Eq. (3)). This contribution, however, is not solved exactly, since the procedure described in [42] just provides an approximation of the dynamic boundary condition.

Finally, we provide below the expressions for the global kinetic energy and the global surface energy at the initial time:

$$\mathcal{E}_{k0} = \frac{\pi \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2 R^4}{2n}, \quad \mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} = 2\pi R \sigma \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}_{k0}}{\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0}} = \frac{\text{We}}{4n}. \tag{36}$$

Table 1
Analytical solutions for the six-mode drop with $We = 8.4$ and $Re = 367$.

Lamb [42]		Linear theory (Appendix D)	
β	ω	β	ω
3.750	114.564	3.434	114.503

Note that the ratio between the former energy components only depends on the Weber number and on the number of modes.

The solution described up to here provides an accurate estimation of the oscillating period ω , but slightly overestimates the viscous damping, i.e. the coefficient β . For this reason, in Appendix D we provide the complete solution for the linearized problem. This leads to the exact linear dispersion relation which, however, is solved numerically, since its roots cannot be found explicitly.

4.1.1. Six-mode oscillating drop

Here we consider the case with $n = 6$ (namely, the six-mode oscillating drop). The dimensionless numbers are $We = 8.4$ and $Re = 367$, corresponding, for example, to a water drop of about 0.22 mm diameter (typical of drizzle), while the perturbation parameter is $\epsilon = 0.2$, thus representing a fully nonlinear case. Despite this, the theoretical results of the previous section are still useful to check the evolution after the initial transient stages, when the nonlinearities are stronger. For longer times, in fact, the oscillations decrease because of the viscous dissipation and the linear theory holds true. The Table 1 summarizes the values computed from the exact linear dispersion relation and those obtained through the approximate solutions (29) and (30). The Lamb [42] approach overestimates the damping parameter of about 9.2%, whereas the angular frequency practically coincides with the one predicted by the linear theory.

The Fig. 2 displays some snapshots of the evolution of the pressure field for the six-mode drop with $N = R/\Delta r = 400$. The symbol P_0 indicates the Laplace pressure for the circular drop at the equilibrium. Panel (a) shows the initial condition while panel (b) the instant of maximum deformation of the free surface. The nonlinear features of the motion are highlighted in panel (c), where the second mode of oscillation (namely the twelve-mode) is depicted. In panel (d) at $t \simeq T$ ($T = 2\pi/\omega$ being the oscillation period predicted by the linear theory) the drop reaches its second maximum elongation, while in panel (e), it returns to its initial circular shape with a lower energy content due to viscous dissipation. Beyond this point (panel (f)), the oscillation amplitude becomes smaller, so that the evolution proceeds in agreement with the linear theory.

The convergence of the global kinetic energy of the drop, namely \mathcal{E}_K , is displayed in Fig. 3 for $N = R/\Delta r = 50, 100, 200, 400$. Here, the letters correspond to the instants depicted in Fig. 2. The order of convergence computed with the L_1 -norm is about 1.2 over a time span of 12 periods. In all simulations, the speed of sound has been set as $c_0 = 12 a \omega$, guaranteeing the fulfillment of the relation (13).

The comparison with linear theory is provided in Fig. 4 for $N = 400$ and $t > 4T$. After this instant, in fact, the nonlinear effects decrease and the oscillations become almost sinusoidal. Along with \mathcal{E}_K , this figure also shows the behavior of the overall energy dissipated by the numerical scheme, namely:

$$Q_{diss} = \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_{diss} d\tau. \quad (37)$$

This term slightly overestimates the theoretical prediction since, in addition to the dissipation due to the viscous forces, it also contains the dissipation induced by the numerical terms (i.e. shifting and Riemann fluxes). Apart from this, the overall agreement is good. Furthermore, the period of oscillation of the SPH outputs is close to the one predicted by linear theory, as reported in Fig. 4 for $t > 10T$ (the theoretical span of one period is displayed to facilitate comparison). Fig. 5 presents a close-up view of the kinetic energy for different spatial resolutions compared to the linear theory. A clear convergence towards the analytical solution is observed.

Finally, Fig. 6 shows the different energy terms during the overall evolution for the finest spatial resolution, i.e., $N = 400$. In particular, the energy components \mathcal{W}_σ and \mathcal{E}_σ show a good agreement, except for small discrepancies that are observed during the early stages of the evolution. We recall that \mathcal{W}_σ and \mathcal{E}_σ , which at the continuum are identical, are computed in two different ways (i.e., the former through the CSF model and the latter through the Level-Set function). This serves as a cross-check of the model accuracy and robustness.

4.2. Coalescence and break-up of viscous drops

As explained in [3,44], the phenomena of drop coalescence and break-up represent challenging problems both in terms of physical/mathematical description and numerical modeling.

From a theoretical point of view, the assumption that the free surface becomes smooth immediately after the onset of coalescence or remains so up to the moment of breakup leads to singular self-similar solutions of the Navier–Stokes equations (see, for example, [45]). As shown in [3], these similarity solutions can be avoided by dropping the standard kinematic boundary condition (that prescribed that fluid particles along the free surface remain there during the evolution) and regarding the topological transition as a particular case of an interface formation/disappearance process. This general approach allows a free-surface cusp to persist for finite times and either to propagate away from the initial contact point of two volumes leading to their coalescence or to “sever” a liquid filament connecting them in the case of breakup.

Fig. 2. Pressure evolution for a large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop. The spatial resolution is $N = R/\Delta r = 400$. [Link Video No 1.](#)

Regarding the numerical modeling, different approaches have been developed to describe the above phenomena. About coalescence, a Finite Difference technique with an Immersed Boundary Method is adopted in [11], while [46] used a Finite Volume scheme and tracked the interface explicitly by connected marker points. Finally, a Volume Of Fluid approach with Finite Volume technique is implemented in, e.g., [10,12]. Note that in the cases where interface is tracked (as in [46]), coalescence is obtained through “ad hoc” techniques by merging the interfaces when their separation is below a certain threshold distance.

In this framework, the use of SPH is expected to be advantageous. Indeed, as described in [15], the SPH does not need an explicit tracking of the free surface and the kinematic and dynamic boundary conditions are satisfied in a global integral way. As shown in the next section, this allows one to recover some of the specific features of the drop evolution without the inclusion of any specific treatment of the free surface.

Fig. 3. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop: initial stages of the evolution of the kinetic energy for different spatial resolutions. The letters correspond to the instants depicted in Fig. 2. The symbol \mathcal{E}_{k0} denotes the value of the kinetic energy at the initial time.

Fig. 4. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop: long-time evolution of the kinetic energy and of the dissipated energy Q_{diss} . The spatial resolution is $N = 400$. The letter f corresponds to the last instant depicted in Fig. 2. The symbol \mathcal{E}_{k0} denotes the value of the kinetic energy at the initial time.

Fig. 5. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop: zoom of the evolution of the kinetic energy for different spatial resolutions and comparison with the analytical solution from linear theory as in Table 1. The symbol \mathcal{E}_{k0} denotes the value of the kinetic energy at the initial time.

4.2.1. Coalescing drops

Fig. 7 displays the initial configuration of two circular drops of radius R approaching each other with a constant velocity U_0 . The initial distance between them is equal to the kernel radius, namely R_W , which is the minimum distance needed to avoid an instantaneous interaction between the particles belonging to different drops. The initial surface tension energy of the fluid system is $\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} = 2\pi\sigma R$, while its asymptotic value for long times is assumed to be that associated with a single circular drop generated by the merging of the initial drops. Since the latter drop has radius $R_\infty = \sqrt{2}R$, the asymptotic energy of the surface tension is $\mathcal{E}_{\sigma\infty} = \sqrt{2}\pi\sigma R$. and, therefore, the overall variation of surface tension energy is $\Delta\mathcal{E} = (\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0} - \mathcal{E}_{\sigma\infty}) = 2\pi\sigma R(2 - \sqrt{2})$. Denoting by M_0

Fig. 6. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop: long-time evolution of the main energy components for the finest spatial resolution (namely, $N = 400$). The symbol \mathcal{E}_{k0} denotes the value of the kinetic energy at the initial time.

Fig. 7. Sketch of the initial configuration for the problem of coalescing drops. The symbol U_0 indicates the initial velocity of each drop, while R and R_W are respectively the radius and the distance between them (equal to the radius of the kernel function).

the initial mass of the fluid system, we define the reference velocity of the problem as:

$$U_{ref} = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta\mathcal{E}}{M_0}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma(2 - \sqrt{2})}{R}} \tag{38}$$

By definition, this implies $We = (2 - \sqrt{2})$, while the Reynolds number has been set equal to 242. These values correspond, for example, to a water drop of 1 mm radius. Furthermore, we require $U_0 \ll U_{ref}$ to guarantee that the physical evolution is governed by the surface tensions and that the initial kinetic energy is not preponderant. Specifically, we choose $U_0/U_{ref} = 0.041$. Incidentally, we highlight that in the works on drop coalescence the dimensionless numbers are generally defined through the collision velocity U_0 instead of U_{ref} . In that case, we would obtain $Re_0 = 9.9$ and $We_0 = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$.

The initial stages of the impact are shown in Fig. 8 where the modulus of the velocity is plotted. Hereinafter, $t_0 = 0.5R_W/U_{ref}$ indicates the theoretical time instant when the drops first touch. During the early stages of the evolution, large velocity values are observed at the extremities of the contact line (top panels of Fig. 8). These values slowly decrease while the drops deform but remains localized close to the free surface. The longer time evolution (see Fig. 9) confirms that the drops eventually merge in one single volume. The overall dynamics is rather complex but, according to the results of Section 4.1, it can be essentially traced back to a two-mode oscillating drop.

Fig. 10 displays the energy balance for the coalescing system. In this figure the time history of the surface tension energy, namely $(\mathcal{E}_\sigma - \mathcal{E}_{\sigma0})/\Delta\mathcal{E}$, has been moved upward to match with the term $(-W_\sigma)/\Delta\mathcal{E}$. This allows us to highlight the generation of an energy gap at the initial time, i.e. when the drops first touch. This phenomenon, which is described in detail in [3,44], is briefly sketched in Fig. 11. During the early stages of coalescence, part of the free surface is trapped inside the two drop volumes, and two cusps are

Fig. 8. Coalescing drops: early stages of the evolution for $We = (2 - \sqrt{2})$, $Re = 242$ and spatial resolution $N = 800$. [Link Video No 2.](#)

Fig. 9. Coalescing drops: long time evolution for $We = (2 - \sqrt{2})$, $Re = 242$ and spatial resolution $N = 800$.

generated and propagate far from the initial contact point (see panels (b) and (c)). This dynamics holds up until the cusps disappear and a smooth surface develops (panel (d)). The length ℓ of the free surface that is incorporated inside the merged volumes leads to the energy gap $\delta\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma\ell$ that is observed at the initial time in Fig. 10. This figure also shows that the total energy of the system, namely \mathcal{E}_{tot} , is conserved during the evolution. Such an energy term is obtained by integrating in time the first expression of Eq. (21) and corresponds, in fact, to the summation of all the energy contributions, that is:

$$\mathcal{E}_{tot} = \mathcal{E}_K + \mathcal{E}_C - Q_{diss} - \mathcal{W}_\sigma. \tag{39}$$

Fig. 10. Energy balance for the coalescing drops. The time history of the term $(\mathcal{E}_\sigma - \mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0})/\Delta\mathcal{E}$ has been shifted upward to match with the term $(-\mathcal{W}_\sigma/\Delta\mathcal{E})$ and show the initial gap caused by the coalescing phenomenon.

Fig. 11. Sketches of the phenomenon of drop coalescence: (a) drops approaching with constant velocity U_0 , (b) initial contact point, (c) free-surface trapping and cusp propagation, (d) formation of new smooth surfaces.

Accordingly, \mathcal{E}_{tot} is monitored to check that the errors caused by the numerical time integration are negligible in comparison to the physical energy contributions.

Fig. 12 contains some details of initial contact point between the drops and of the generation and propagation of cusps for a coarse and a fine spatial resolutions (left and right columns respectively). Apart from minor differences, the overall dynamics is very similar, proving that the coalescence phenomenon is well-described by the SPH scheme. The trapping of a segment of the free surface inside the fluid volumes is also evinced by the discrepancy between the particle velocity at the free surface, namely u_y , and the velocity u_y^{FS} of the free surface (red solid lines in the figure). Specifically, the symbol u_y refers to the y -component of the velocity of the free-surface particle closest to the cusp location, whereas the symbol u_y^{FS} denotes the measured velocity of the cusp itself, identified on the free-surface defined by the Level-set function (red line in Fig. 12). u_y^{FS} has been evaluated in the post-processing stage on the base of the different snapshots of the flow evolution which are printed every $\Delta t_{print} = 2.5 \times 10^{-4} t U_{ref}/R$.

In fact, the latter one is significantly larger than the former during the very initial stages of the evolution (middle panels of Fig. 12). For longer times, the discrepancy reduces and eventually disappears (bottom panels), indicating the recovering of a smooth free surface.

Finally, Fig. 13 provides the convergence of the energy components \mathcal{E}_K , \mathcal{E}_σ and \mathcal{W}_σ for $N = 50, 100, 200, 400, 800$. The time along the abscissa is translated by t_0 so that the zero value represents the theoretical instant when the drops first touch. This time shift was made necessary to allow for a trustworthy comparison between different spatial resolutions. Indeed, the initial drops distance R_W changes according to the specific discretization (see Fig. 7), resulting in different time instants for the initial impact. Despite this expedient, the early stages of the evolution significantly differ from the coarsest and to the finest spatial resolution. This is due to the fact that the drops actually start interacting before they touch, as a consequence of the SPH smoothing interpolation. This

Fig. 12. Initial stages of the coalescing process for $N = 100$ (left column) and $N = 400$ (right column). The symbol U_y indicates the y -component of the velocity field at the free-surface, whereas U_y^{FS} is the y -component of the velocity of the free surface (red solid lines). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

phenomenon (which is a numerical effect and strongly depends on the spatial resolution) combines with the surface tension, leading to a complex initial dynamics. A possible choice would be to inhibit the interaction between the fluid patches before they actually merge using a visibility criterion as, for example, in [47,48]. However, this choice would have introduced some arbitrariness in determining the exact moment of contact between the drops. For this reason, the kernel interpolation was left unchanged. In any case, despite the complexity of the initial dynamics, all terms converge and the overall error for the energy balance maintains below 0.01% $\Delta\mathcal{E}$.

4.2.2. Break-up and subsequent coalescence

In comparison to drop coalescence, the break-up phenomenon is, to some extent, more complex to describe, both in terms of physical and theoretical features. This is due by presence of a very thin thread of fluid that suddenly breaks up, dividing the initial

Fig. 13. Coalescing drops: convergence analysis for the global kinetic energy (top), the surface tensions energy (middle) and the work done by the surface tension (bottom).

volume in two different drops. This process is characterized by the occurrence of a cusped profile at the pinch-off point that, after the break-up, rapidly rearranges in two regular free-surface interfaces. For more details on the underlying physics the interested reader is referred to, e.g., [2].

Two-mode oscillating drop. We first consider the case of a drop subjected to a two-mode oscillation of large amplitude. In particular we set $a = 1.25R$, $Re = 194$ and $We = 9.38$, which approximately corresponds to a water drop of radius $5.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m. Using the last relation in (36), we find $\mathcal{E}_{k0}/\mathcal{E}_{\sigma0} = 1.1725$. This ratio plays an important role in the characterization of the break-up phenomenon, since, as pointed out in [7], the two-mode drop is expected to break for $\mathcal{E}_{k0}/\mathcal{E}_{\sigma0} > 0.75$. In fact, the latter value is exactly the one considered in [19] (with the same spatial resolution adopted here) where no break-up is detected in the simulations. Incidentally, we highlight that the criterion described in [7] only applies to two-dimensional problems and to two-mode systems, while some changes are expected in three-dimensional cases and for a larger number of modes. Aside from this, such a criterion seems to be weakly influenced by the viscosity, at least for large enough Reynolds numbers.

Fig. 14 shows the main stages of the evolution of the oscillation drop for $N = R/\Delta r = 400$. The top right panel displays the maximum elongation of the initial drop in two bumps tied by a thin fluid thread. After this instant, the bumps start moving closer (middle left panel), while the thread becomes thinner and thinner and eventually breaks (middle right panel), generating tiny secondary drops and large acoustic waves that propagate inside the fluid bulk. Just before the breaking time the fluid thread is just two-particle thick, that is $2\Delta r = R/200$. After this stage, the two separated drops continue moving closer and, finally, merge (bottom right panel).

Since the pressure oscillations generated by the break-up and by the subsequent coalescence are rather intense (about $120P_0$ and $10P_0$ respectively), a larger sound speed is used for this numerical simulation, namely $c_0 = 31a\omega$. The pressure in the tiny fluid drops generated after the break-up (see the details in the panel (d) of Fig. 14) is much larger (about $200P_0$) and would, in principle, raise some doubts about the validity of the weakly-compressibility assumption. In any case, the spatial resolution is not fine enough to represent their evolution which, in any case, is not relevant for the overall dynamics.

A more detailed insight is provided by the analysis of the energy balance of the fluid system. This is illustrated in Fig. 15 where the different energy components are shown along with an enlarged view of the break-up and coalescence phenomena (bottom plot). During the early evolution \mathcal{W}_σ and \mathcal{E}_σ show a good agreement, confirming the dynamics described in Section 4.1. The overall behavior changes, however, when the break-up phenomenon occurs. In this case the work done by the surface tension forces, namely \mathcal{W}_σ , undergoes an abrupt discontinuity (bottom panel of Fig. 15). This energy loss corresponds to the energy spent to separate the

Fig. 14. Pressure evolution for a large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop. The spatial resolution is $N = R/\Delta r = 400$. [Link Video No 3](#).

thin thread between the bumps. Conversely, the signal of the surface tension energy, \mathcal{E}_σ , maintains regular, since the overall length of the fluid system undergoes minor changes.

The opposite behavior is observed during the coalescence stage, that is in the panels (e) and (f) of Fig. 14. Indeed, the surface tension energy \mathcal{E}_σ experiences a sudden energy loss caused by the free-surface entrapment, in analogy to the dynamics described in Section Section 4.2.1. Conversely, the work \mathcal{W}_σ is less affected by the coalescence phenomenon, even though a larger dissipation is observed after the coalescence stage is completed. Remarkably, we observe that in the subsequent evolution \mathcal{W}_σ and \mathcal{E}_σ match together again, proving that the energy lost by \mathcal{W}_σ during the break-up is approximately equal to the energy lost by \mathcal{E}_σ during the coalescence stage.

Six-mode oscillating drop. Continuing the analysis of the previous section, we described here the evolution of a six-mode drops subjected to large excitations. Table 2 briefly summarized the dimensionless parameters considered in the numerical simulations.

Fig. 15. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop: Top: long-time evolution of the main energy components for $N = 400$. Bottom: Enlarged view in the time range where break-up and coalescence phenomena take place. The letters refer to the panels in Fig. 14.

Table 2
Dimensionless numbers used for the simulations of a single drop subjected to large oscillations.

$\epsilon = a/R$	Re	We	$\mathcal{E}_{k0}/\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0}$	$P_{Max}(t=0)/P_0$
0.20	367	8.4	0.35	8.00
0.35	642	26	1.07	13.3
0.40	733	34	1.40	15.0
0.50	916	53	2.19	18.5
0.60	1100	76	3.15	22.0
0.70	1283	103	4.29	25.5

These are chosen so that the parameter of the amplitude excitation, namely ϵ , increases gradually, while the ratio $\chi = Re^2/We$ maintains constant and equal to 16,000. As shown in Section 4.1 and in Appendix D for the linear solutions, this latter parameter discerns the particular regime of motion for a given number of modes. The overall dynamics is, however, expected to rapidly evolve away from the linear theory. This is confirmed by the top left plot of Fig. 16 where the evolution of the free surface is displayed at the instant of maximum elongation for different values of ϵ . The drop tends to elongate following the six directions of oscillations and, for the largest value of ϵ , eventually breaks, generating six smaller drops (top right panel of the same Figure). In this case the ratio $\mathcal{E}_{k0}/\mathcal{E}_{\sigma 0}$ is about six times larger than the criterion proposed in [7].

Incidentally, we observe that the dynamics after the break-up is slightly asymmetric due to the sensitivity to small variations occurring in the fluid particle distributions.

The time history of the kinetic energy for the different values of ϵ is displayed in the bottom plot of Fig. 16. For $\epsilon < 0.7$, a peak is observed when the drop reaches the maximum elongation. Conversely, for $\epsilon = 0.7$ the peak does not occur because part of the kinetic energy is employed for the break-up phenomenon and a sort of plateau is observed up to the coalescence stage. This dynamics is similar to the one described in Fig. 15 for the two-mode drop.

A more detailed description of the energy balance for the six-mode system is provided in Fig. 17. In particular, the top plot displays the evolution of the energy components for $\epsilon = 0.6$, while the case $\epsilon = 0.7$ is reported in the bottom plot. Similarly to what already observed in the previous Sections, \mathcal{E}_{σ} and \mathcal{W}_{σ} show a fairly good agreement for $\epsilon = 0.6$ (non breaking case) during all the simulation. Conversely, for $\epsilon = 0.7$ the same energy components detach during the break-up occurrence and reconnect at the drop coalescing (bottom plot of Fig. 17). The dynamics is essentially similar to that described in Fig. 15 for the two-mode drop.

Fig. 16. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop. Top-left: maximum droplet elongation varying the amplitude motion a , from $0.35R$ up to $0.70R$. Top-right: Pressure field just after the break-up stage for the amplitude motion $a = 0.70R$. Bottom: time histories of the kinetic energy during the early stages of the evolution. [Link Video No 4](#).

Fig. 17. Large amplitude oscillation of a 2D liquid drop. Energy balance for $\epsilon = 0.6$ (non breaking drop, top panel) and $\epsilon = 0.7$ (breaking drop, bottom panel).

5. Discussion and conclusions

In the proposed work a study on the phenomena of viscous drop coalescence and break-up in the presence of surface tension has been carried on through the use of the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH). Thanks to its nature, SPH allowed for a straightforward modeling of the free-surface evolution and for a direct analysis of the energy balance during the drop evolution.

This latter aspect has been inspected by using two different approaches: *i*) the energy associated with the surface tension has been calculated through the relation $\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma \mathcal{L}_F$ where the free-surface length was obtained through a Level-Set function, *ii*) the work \mathcal{W}_σ made by the surface tension force has been computed through the energy balance of the SPH scheme. These contributions are identical when the evolution of the free surface is regular. This has been shown, for example, in Section 4.1 for the problem of the oscillating drop. Conversely, they differ when singularities occur along the free surface, as, for example, during coalescence and break-up (Sections Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2).

The use of such a compound approach allowed us to describe the drop dynamics accurately and to highlight some specific features. In agreement with the results of [3], the drop coalescence is characterized by the free-surface trapping and the occurrence of propagating cusps, until a novel smooth interface is generated. This behavior induces a loss of energy in \mathcal{E}_σ caused by the disappearance of a certain portion of the free surface. Conversely, \mathcal{W}_σ is weakly affected by this dynamics, since the particle velocity is tangential to the free surface during the trapping process and, therefore, no contribution to the overall work is done.

About the break-up phenomenon, we observed that a certain amount of work is required to separate the thin thread of fluid in two distinct interfaces. Specifically, this corresponds to a sudden loss of work in \mathcal{W}_σ . Conversely, only a minor influence on \mathcal{E}_σ is observed, since the overall length of the free surface is practically unchanged during the break-up. Remarkably, approximately the same amount of energy is lost by \mathcal{E}_σ during the subsequent drop coalescence. This phenomenon, which probably conceals some specific physical process, is not clear at the moment and deserves a future investigation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M. Antuono: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **S. Marrone:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **A. Colagrossi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix A. Proof of the relations in Eq. (4)

In this Section and in the subsequent ones the subscripts i, j, k indicate the components of vectors and tensors. In particular, the Levi-Civita tensor is denoted by ϵ_{ijk} and the identity matrix by δ_{ij} .

Let us consider the first relation in Eq. (4). If $\partial\Omega$ is a *closed* oriented surface (hereinafter we drop the subscript ‘F’ for the sake of simplicity), we can apply the divergence theorem and write:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\partial\Omega} \kappa n_i dS &= - \int_{\partial\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_j} \right) n_i dS = - \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_j} \right) dV \\ &= - \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_i} \right) dV = - \int_{\partial\Omega} n_j \frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_i} dS, \end{aligned}$$

and the first relation in Eq. (4) follows from the identity $n_j^2 = 1$.

Now, let us consider the second relation in (4). Using the Levi-Civita tensor to express the cross product and the divergence theorem, we obtain:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{r} \times (\kappa_m \mathbf{n}) dS = \int_{\partial\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} x_j \left(\frac{\partial n_s}{\partial x_s} \right) n_k dS = \int_{\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(x_j \frac{\partial n_s}{\partial x_s} \right) dV$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} \delta_{jk} \frac{\partial n_s}{\partial x_s} dV}_{=0} + \int_{\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} x_j \frac{\partial^2 n_s}{\partial x_s \partial x_k} dV \\
&= \int_{\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_s} \left(x_j \frac{\partial n_s}{\partial x_k} \right) dV - \int_{\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} \delta_{js} \frac{\partial n_s}{\partial x_k} dV \\
&= \underbrace{\int_{\partial\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} x_j \frac{\partial n_s}{\partial x_k} n_s dS}_{=0} - \int_{\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_k} dV = - \int_{\partial\Omega} \epsilon_{ijk} n_j n_j dS \\
&= - \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{n}) dS = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that $\epsilon_{ijk} \delta_{jk} = 0$, because δ_{jk} is a symmetric tensor.

Appendix B. Details on the derivation of the energy balance

In this section, we prove the relation (6). First, we recall the transport theorem for a *material* surface S (see, for example, [49,50]):

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_S \psi dS = \int_S \left[\frac{D\psi}{Dt} + \psi \operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u} \right] dS, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where ψ is a generic scalar field and:

$$\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Following [50], the above expression can be rearranged as follows:

$$\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u} = \operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u}_{tan} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \nabla \cdot \mathbf{n}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{tan} = \mathbf{u} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n}$ (a brief proof of the above identity is provided at the end of this section). If we apply the definition (B.2) to the field \mathbf{n} and use the identity $\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{n} = 0$, we obtain $\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{n} = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{n}$. Then, introducing the curvature as $\kappa = -\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{n}$ (i.e. twice the mean curvature), Eq. (B.3) becomes:

$$\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u} = \operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u}_{tan} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \kappa. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

As pointed out in [50], the term $\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u}_{tan}$ allows for the use of the Stokes theorem along the surface. Indeed, using the standard identities of the Levi-Civita tensor, it is possible to prove the following identity:

$$\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u}_{tan} = \mathbf{n} \cdot [\nabla \times (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u})]. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Hence, applying the transport theorem (B.1) to $\psi = 1$ and, then, substituting Eq. (B.4), we find:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_S dS = \int_S \operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u} dS = \int_S \operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u}_{tan} dS - \int_S (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \kappa dS. \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Now, using the expression (B.5) and the Stokes theorem, we obtain:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_S dS = \oint_{\mathcal{C}} (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u}) \cdot d\boldsymbol{\ell} - \int_S (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \kappa dS. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

If S is a closed material surface, $\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$ and the above relation simplifies as follows:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_S dS = - \int_S (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \kappa dS, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

that corresponds to Eq. (6).

B.1. Proof of the relation (B.3)

Below we give the proof of the relation (B.3). Using the definition (B.2), we compute the surface divergence of the field $\mathbf{u}_{tan} = \mathbf{u} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n}$. In particular, denoting $\alpha = (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n})$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u}_{tan} &= \frac{\partial (u_i - \alpha n_i)}{\partial x_i} - n_i \frac{\partial (u_i - \alpha n_i)}{\partial x_j} n_j \\
&= \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x_i} n_i - \alpha \frac{\partial n_i}{\partial x_i} - n_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} n_j + (n_i n_i) \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x_j} n_j + \alpha n_i \frac{\partial n_i}{\partial x_j} n_j \\
&= \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x_i} n_i - \alpha \frac{\partial n_i}{\partial x_i} - n_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} n_j + \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x_j} n_j + \frac{\alpha}{2} \frac{\partial (n_i n_i)}{\partial x_j} n_j.
\end{aligned}$$

Since $(n_i n_i) = 1$, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u}_{tan} &= \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} - \alpha \frac{\partial n_i}{\partial x_i} - n_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} n_j = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \nabla \cdot \mathbf{n} \\ &= \operatorname{div}_S \mathbf{u} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \nabla \cdot \mathbf{n}, \end{aligned}$$

that is the relation (B.3).

B.2. Proof of the relation (B.5)

Here we give the proof of the relation (B.5). Using the standard identities of the Levi-Civita tensor, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{n} \cdot [\nabla \times (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u})] &= \varepsilon_{ijk} \varepsilon_{kpq} n_i \frac{\partial(n_p u_q)}{\partial x_j} = (\delta_{ip} \delta_{jq} - \delta_{iq} \delta_{jp}) n_i \frac{\partial(n_p u_q)}{\partial x_j} \\ &= n_i \frac{\partial(n_i u_j)}{\partial x_j} - n_i \frac{\partial(n_j u_i)}{\partial x_j} = n_i \frac{\partial n_i}{\partial x_j} u_j + n_i^2 \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_j} - n_i \frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_j} u_i - n_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} n_j \\ &= \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \kappa - \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \end{aligned}$$

where the identity $n_i^2 = 1$ is used in the last identity. Finally, using the expressions (B.2) and (B.3), we obtain the thesis.

Appendix C. Details on the results of Section 2.1

Here we provide the details of derivation of some results described in Section 2.1. We recall that the unit vector normal to $\partial\Omega$ is defined as $\mathbf{n} = \nabla C_\epsilon / \|\nabla C_\epsilon\|$ and points outward, while $\delta_\epsilon = 2\|\nabla C_\epsilon\|$. The color function is assumed to be smooth.

First, we show that δ_ϵ converges to a Dirac distribution along $\partial\Omega$, hereinafter indicated by the symbol $\delta_{\partial\Omega}$. To this purpose, it is more convenient to prove the following result:

$$\mathbf{n} \delta_\epsilon \rightharpoonup \mathbf{n} \delta_{\partial\Omega} \tag{C.1}$$

where the arrow indicates the weak convergence. Hence, the desired outcome is obtained by multiplying the expression (C.1) by \mathbf{n} . Now, let us assume that f is a generic scalar function belonging to $H^1(\Omega) \cap L^1(\partial\Omega)$. Applying the divergence theorem, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_\Omega f \nabla C_\epsilon dV &= \int_\Omega \nabla (f C_\epsilon) dV - \int_\Omega \nabla f C_\epsilon dV \\ &= \int_{\partial\Omega} f C_\epsilon(0) \mathbf{n} dS - \int_\Omega \nabla f C_\epsilon dV. \end{aligned}$$

Using the properties in Eq. (8), we obtain:

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_\Omega f \nabla C_\epsilon dV = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial\Omega} f \mathbf{n} dS.$$

Finally, the relation (C.1) is achieved by noting that $\mathbf{n} \delta_\epsilon = 2 \nabla C_\epsilon$.

Below we prove the equivalence between the relations (9) and (10). Starting from Eq. (9) and recalling that $\kappa = -(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{n})$, we write:

$$\frac{\mathbf{F}^{(S)}}{2\sigma} = \kappa \mathbf{n} \|\nabla C_\epsilon\| = -(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{n}) \nabla C_\epsilon \tag{C.2}$$

Working by components, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{F_i^{(S)}}{2\sigma} &= \frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial C_\epsilon}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(n_j \frac{\partial C_\epsilon}{\partial x_i} \right) - n_j \frac{\partial^2 C_\epsilon}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (n_j n_i \|\nabla C_\epsilon\|) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(n_j \frac{\partial C_\epsilon}{\partial x_j} \right) + \frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial C_\epsilon}{\partial x_j} \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (n_j n_i \|\nabla C_\epsilon\|) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\|\nabla C_\epsilon\|) + \frac{\partial n_j}{\partial x_i} n_j \|\nabla C_\epsilon\| \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} [\|\nabla C_\epsilon\| (n_i n_j - \delta_{ij})]. \end{aligned}$$

The identity $n_j^2 = 1$ has been used in the last step. Hence, we define:

$$\mathbb{T}^{(S)} = 2\sigma \|\nabla C_\epsilon\| (\delta_{ij} - n_i n_j). \tag{C.3}$$

that is the tensor introduced in the expression (10).

Appendix D. Solution for the oscillating drop in zero gravity from the linear theory

We consider the following stream function:

$$\psi = \epsilon \psi_0 \cos(n\theta) \left[\left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^n + C_n J_n \left(\xi \frac{r}{R} \right) \right] \exp \left(-\frac{\nu \xi^2}{R^2} t \right) \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where ψ_0 is a dimensional coefficient, J_n is the n th-order Bessel function of the first kind, C_n is a dimensionless coefficient and ξ is a dimensionless parameter. The latter is related to the damping coefficient by the expression $\alpha = \xi^2 \nu / R^2$. Incidentally, we highlight that the component of ψ containing the Bessel function represents the rotational part of the velocity field. In particular, the solution for the vorticity reads:

$$\text{rot}(u) = \epsilon \frac{\xi^2 \psi_0}{R^2} C_n \cos(n\theta) J_n \left(\xi \frac{r}{R} \right) \exp \left(-\frac{\nu \xi^2}{R^2} t \right). \quad (\text{D.2})$$

Using the stream function, the continuity equation is satisfied by construction, while the momentum equation gives the following expression for the pressure field:

$$\frac{p}{\rho_0} = \frac{\sigma}{\rho_0 R} - \epsilon \frac{\nu \xi^2 \psi_0}{R^2} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^n \sin(n\theta) \exp \left(-\frac{\nu \xi^2}{R^2} t \right). \quad (\text{D.3})$$

Note that the above equation already includes the leading-order contribution of the surface tensions along the free surface. The free surface position is given by $r_{FS} = R + \epsilon \eta$ and the solution for η is obtained through the linearized kinematic condition at the free surface, leading to:

$$\eta = \frac{n R \psi_0}{\xi^2 \nu} \sin(n\theta) [C_n J_n(\xi) + 1] \exp \left(-\frac{\nu \xi^2}{R^2} t \right). \quad (\text{D.4})$$

The coefficient C_n is obtained by solving the linearized dynamics condition at the free surface along the tangential direction. This reads:

$$C_n = -\frac{2(n-1)n}{[2n(n+1) - \xi^2] J_n(\xi) - 2\xi J_{n-1}(\xi)} \quad (\text{D.5})$$

The final step is to satisfy the linearized dynamics condition at the free surface along the normal direction. To this purpose we need to compute the linearized curvature, that is:

$$\kappa = -\frac{1}{R} - \epsilon n (n^2 - 1) \frac{\psi_0}{\xi^2 \nu R} \sin(n\theta) [C_n J_n(\xi) + 1] \exp \left(-\frac{\nu \xi^2}{R^2} t \right). \quad (\text{D.6})$$

Finally, substituting this expression in the kinematic condition along the normal direction, we find the linear dispersion relation for ξ :

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\xi^6 - 4n^2 \xi^4 + n(n^2 - 1)(8n + \chi) \xi^2 - 4n^2(n^2 - 1)\chi \right] J_n(\xi) \\ & + 2\xi \left[\xi^4 - 2n(n^2 - 1) \xi^2 + n(n^2 - 1)\chi \right] J_{n-1}(\xi) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.7})$$

where:

$$\chi = \frac{\sigma R}{\rho_0 \nu^2} = \frac{\text{Re}^2}{\text{We}}. \quad (\text{D.8})$$

The correct root of Eq. (D.7) is found numerically through the Newton method. The starting point for the algorithm is chosen by using the approximate solution provided by Eq. (27).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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